

Rutor Digisky aerial 2020

Processing Report

07 May 2024

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	867	Camera stations:	815
Flying altitude:	818 m	Tie points:	370,551
Ground resolution:	5.96 cm/pix	Projections:	2,553,517
Coverage area:	25.1 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.395 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
iXM-RS150F, Rodenstoc...	14204 x 10652	50 mm	3.76 x 3.76 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for iXM-RS150F, Rodenstock RS-50mm/Aerial (50mm).

iXM-RS150F, Rodenstock RS-50mm/Aerial (50mm)

817 images

Type	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size
Frame	14204 x 10652	50 mm	3.76 x 3.76 μm

	Value	Error	F	Cx	Cy	B1	B2	K1	K2	K3	K4	P1	P2
F	13743.3	0.038	1.00	-0.08	-0.61	0.18	0.15	-0.10	0.11	-0.09	0.08	-0.01	-0.06
Cx	57.3174	0.0087		1.00	0.04	-0.02	0.03	-0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.01	0.88	-0.01
Cy	-8.78157	0.0093			1.00	-0.13	-0.09	-0.01	0.00	-0.00	0.01	0.00	0.67
B1	0.315167	0.0029				1.00	0.01	0.02	-0.02	0.02	-0.01	0.01	0.01
B2	-0.896992	0.0029					1.00	0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.00	0.01	-0.00
K1	-0.00506231	9.7e-06						1.00	-0.97	0.93	-0.88	-0.01	-0.02
K2	0.0065116	9.1e-05							1.00	-0.99	0.96	0.01	-0.01
K3	0.063094	0.00034								1.00	-0.99	-0.01	0.00
K4	-0.126768	0.00042									1.00	0.01	-0.00
P1	-1.88636e-06	2.3e-07										1.00	0.00
P2	8.44211e-05	2e-07											1.00

Table 2. Calibration coefficients and correlation matrix.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 3. GCP locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated GCP locations are marked with a dot or crossing.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)
18	20.4103	13.1059	10.6057	24.2558	26.4731

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)
7	18.9872	14.9458	17.1342	24.1639	29.6222

Table 4. Check points RMSE.

X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
GCP03	27.4801	-17.9738	-19.7975	38.3425	4.939 (6)
GCP07	11.1898	6.04222	6.81392	14.4274	7.586 (11)
GCP02	-0.576344	-0.910239	-0.0354436	1.07794	0.880 (4)
GCP12	20.6082	-13.3574	-6.16604	25.3207	9.361 (2)
GCP13	-17.8797	19.4439	3.62027	26.6618	15.538 (6)
GCP14	-53.8209	29.3242	17.1002	63.6318	7.573 (6)
GCP04	13.4534	-3.6229	-0.320234	13.9364	9.602 (2)
GCP01	7.06918	-13.7408	6.86747	16.9099	25.861 (11)
GCP08	-0.18408	-14.3295	-20.7021	25.1783	7.108 (6)
GCP15	43.8527	-19.0332	4.24094	47.9928	1.407 (15)
GCP16	2.13234	-6.34851	7.32216	9.92293	0.441 (38)
GCP17	-19.627	-6.15624	-0.23496	20.5712	2.006 (14)
GCP18	4.50713	9.42268	-0.968811	10.49	1.092 (6)
GCP05	6.10044	-1.36875	2.08238	6.58978	0.626 (12)
GCP06	-18.7612	2.75909	4.20062	19.4227	1.375 (13)
GCP09	-3.7706	-1.32908	-17.4568	17.9088	2.196 (10)
GCP10	2.9897	19.104	18.9162	27.0504	2.015 (8)
GCP11	-0.400681	1.50072	-3.12445	3.48925	0.379 (20)
Total	20.4103	13.1059	10.6057	26.4731	7.542

Table 5. Control points.
X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
CP01	-5.1403	9.42173	-10.3172	14.8875	0.692 (17)
CP02	-17.3952	28.0749	-2.35034	33.1107	0.622 (12)
CP06	-13.6064	0.165417	31.9515	34.7284	2.317 (9)
CP07	38.0926	-0.224173	14.8818	40.897	2.382 (5)
CP05	0.221481	22.0909	-16.7647	27.7329	0.281 (7)
CP04	-4.0905	13.9503	-8.84522	17.0171	0.972 (6)
CP03	-23.2729	1.99389	18.4778	29.7831	0.820 (23)
Total	18.9872	14.9458	17.1342	29.6222	1.186

Table 6. Check points.
X - Easting, Y - Northing, Z - Altitude.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 4. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 9.14 m/pix
Point density: 0.012 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General

Cameras	817
Aligned cameras	815
Markers	25
Coordinate system	RDN2008 / UTM zone 32N (N-E) (EPSG::6707)
Rotation angles	Yaw, Pitch, Roll

Tie Points

Points	370,551 of 457,787
RMS reprojection error	0.164229 (0.395351 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.50459 (26.8786 pix)
Mean key point size	1.9327 pix
Point colors	3 bands, uint8
Key points	No
Average tie point multiplicity	7.48877

Alignment parameters

Accuracy	Highest
Generic preselection	Yes
Reference preselection	No
Key point limit	40,000
Key point limit per Mpx	1,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Exclude stationary tie points	No
Guided image matching	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Matching time	1 hours 6 minutes
Matching memory usage	749.31 MB
Alignment time	4 minutes 29 seconds
Alignment memory usage	705.62 MB

Optimization parameters

Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Adaptive camera model fitting	No
Optimization time	9 seconds
Date created	2021:11:15 15:02:18
Software version	1.7.4.13028
File size	62.21 MB

Model

Faces	893,126
Vertices	448,567
Vertex colors	3 bands, uint8
Texture	8,192 x 8,192, 4 bands, uint8

Texturing parameters

Mapping mode	Generic
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	8,192
Enable hole filling	Yes
Enable ghosting filter	Yes
UV mapping time	1 minutes 25 seconds
UV mapping memory usage	875.45 MB
Blending time	7 hours 31 minutes
Blending memory usage	21.83 GB

File size	261.90 MB
System	
Software name	Agisoft Metashape Professional
Software version	2.0.3 build 16960
OS	Windows 64 bit
RAM	63.69 GB
CPU	Intel(R) Core(TM) i9-9900X CPU @ 3.50GHz
GPU(s)	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2060